

MATHEMATICAL SCIENCES

DETERMINATION AND MODELING OF FREQUENCY RESPONSES OF AN INDUSTRIAL CONTROL OBJECT WITH AN ACCELERATION CURVE

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Abstract

Using the known acceleration curve of the second chamber of the Polysius-22 mill, its transfer function was obtained using the original method. From the latter, we determine its phase frequency characteristic, which is necessary for the synthesis of an industrial regulator.

Keywords: acceleration curve, transfer function, frequency characteristics.

To identify the second chamber of the mill Polyzius-22, used its acceleration curve[2], which given in pic.1.

Pic.1. Acceleration curve of the second chamber of the Polysius-22 mill

First, to find the Amplitude-Phase Characteristics, you need to find the transfer function of the object. According to the type of acceleration curve, which has an S-shape and therefore is a second-order inertial link. The transfer function has the following form:

$$W(p) = \frac{k}{(T_1 p + 1)(T_2 p + 1)} \quad (1)$$

We select 6 points on the acceleration curve and substitute them into the formula to find the TF of the second-order inertial link.

Table 1

Selected points from acceleration curve

t	0	1.5	3	4.5	6	7.5	∞
y	0	4	15.5	22	26	29	30

The identification method is given in [2] from which we have:

$$\begin{cases} y_0 B_3 + y_1 B_2 + y_2 B_1 + y_3 = 0 \\ y_1 B_3 + y_2 B_2 + y_3 B_1 + y_4 = 0 \\ y_2 B_3 + y_3 B_2 + y_4 B_1 + y_5 = 0 \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

$$\begin{cases} 0B_3 + 4B_2 + 15.5B_1 + 22 = 0 \\ 4B_3 + 15.5B_2 + 22B_1 + 26 = 0 \\ 15.5B_3 + 22B_2 + 26B_1 + 29 = 0 \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

Calculate: $B_1 = -1.5593; B_2 = 0.5422; B_3 = -0.02497$

Next, determine the roots of the cubic equation:

$$\lambda^3 + B_1 \lambda^2 + B_2 \lambda + B_3 = 0 \quad (4)$$

$$\lambda^3 + (-1.5593)\lambda^2 + 0.5422\lambda + (-0.02497) = 0 \quad (5)$$

$$\lambda_1 = 1; \lambda_2 = p = 0.054; \lambda_3 = q = 0.427 \quad (6)$$

In order to find T_1 и T_2 we use the formula below:

$$T_1 = \frac{-\Delta t}{\ln p}; T_2 = \frac{-\Delta t}{\ln q} \quad (7)$$

$$T_1 = \frac{-1.5}{\ln(0.054)} = 0.514; T_2 = \frac{-1.5}{\ln(0.427)} = 1.763 \quad (8)$$

$$k = \frac{y}{x} = \frac{30}{10} = 3 \quad (9)$$

Substituting all the found values for the desired ones, our transfer function has the following form:

$$W(p) = \frac{3}{(0.514p+1)(1.763p+1)} \quad (10)$$

To determine the frequency response of an object, we transform the TF using Fourier.

$$P \rightarrow j\omega$$

$$W(j\omega) = \frac{3}{(0.514j\omega+1)(1.763j\omega+1)} \quad (11)$$

$$W(j\omega) = \frac{3(1-0.91\omega^2)}{1+0.26\omega^2+3.11\omega^2+0.82\omega^4} - j \frac{3(0.514\omega+1.763\omega)}{1+0.26\omega^2+3.11\omega^2+0.82\omega^4} \quad (12)$$

Accordinging this we know that:

$$P(\omega) = \frac{3(1-0.91\omega^2)}{1+0.26\omega^2+3.11\omega^2+0.82\omega^4} \quad (13)$$

$$Q(\omega) = -\frac{3(0.514\omega+1.763\omega)}{1+0.26\omega^2+3.11\omega^2+0.82\omega^4} \quad (14)$$

Formulas for calculating the amplitude frequency and phase frequency responses:

$$A(\omega) = \sqrt{P^2(\omega) + Q^2(\omega)} \quad (15)$$

$$\varphi(\omega) = \arctan \frac{Q(\omega)}{P(\omega)} \quad (16)$$

$$A(\omega) = \frac{3}{\sqrt{1+3.37\omega^2+0.82\omega^4}} \quad (17)$$

$$\varphi(\omega) = -\arctg \frac{(0.514\omega+1.763\omega)}{(1-0.91\omega^2)} \quad (18)$$

The required frequency response is obtained by modeling in the VisSim

Below are frequency response graphs:

Pic.2. AFR graph on VisSim

Pic.3. PFR graph on VisSim

Pic.4. Amplitude-phase frequency response graph on VisSim

Based on the experimental acceleration curve of the control object, it was identified using a special method. The model of the control object is obtained in the form of a transfer function from which any frequency responses of the control object necessary for the synthesis of industrial (not ideal) regulators of automatic control systems by this process are easily obtained.

References

1 Adambaev M.D. Automatic control in the electric power industry. Applied mathematics and identification. Study guide. – Almaty: KazNTU, 2015. [Published in Russian]

2 Adambaev M.D. Determination of the dynamic structure and parameters of industrial control facilities. Scientific publication (monograph). – Almaty: TST Company, 2018. [Published in Russian]

3 Planning an experiment in the study of technological processes /K. Hartmann, E. Lezki, W. Schafer. – Moscow: MIR Publishing House, 1977. [Published in Russian]

4 Andrievskaya N. V. Identification of control systems: textbook. handbook for universities / N. V. Andrievskaya, N.N. Matushkin, A.A. Yuzhakov - Perm: Publishing House of Perm. National research. Polytechnic University, 2016-170 p. [Published in Russian]